

Determination of Stability Constants of the Complexes of 4-Hydroxy-3-aldehydobiphenyl with Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Mg^{2+}

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Complexation equilibria of metal complexes of Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Mg^{2+} with 4-hydroxy-3-aldehydobiphenyl have been studied potentiometrically. The proton dissociation constant of the reagent and the dissociation constants of its metal complexes have been determined by Bjerrum-Calvin pH titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ and at ionic strength of $\mu = 0.1 M$ in 75 : 25 v/v dioxane-water medium. The order of the stability constants of the chelates was found to be $\text{Cu} > \text{Zn} > \text{Co} > \text{Ni} > \text{Mg}$.

LITERATURE indicates that no work on the stability constants of 4-hydroxy-3-aldehydobiphenyl and its metal complexes has been carried out. In the present study, the successive stability constants of the complexes of 4-hydroxy-3-aldehydobiphenyl with various bivalent metal ions have been determined potentiometrically following the Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti.

Experimental

The aldehyde 4-hydroxy-3-aldehydobiphenyl was synthesised in the laboratory using the modified Duff method². The crude product was repeatedly crystallised to get an analytically pure sample, m. p. 102° . The purity of the compound was tested by tlc and elemental analysis. (Found : C, 78.81 ; H, 5.05. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2$; C, 78.8 ; H, 5.05%).

The Corning model 12 precision research pH meter, with arrangement for normal and expanded scale, was used for pH measurements. The changes in pH can be measured with an accuracy of 0.005 pH unit.

The dioxane used was purified by method described in Vogel⁴. Distilled water, redistilled over alkaline KMnO_4 was used throughout the investigation. The free acid, the free acid plus the ligand and the mixture of metal ion containing the acid and the ligand were titrated against standard carbonate free sodium hydroxide (1.04 M). The solutions of metal perchlorates were prepared from A. R. grade oxides or carbonates and were standardised by EDTA titrations⁵. The pH metric titrations were carried out in an inert atmosphere by bubbling oxygen free nitrogen gas through the solutions. All the measurements were carried out at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ in 75 : 25 v/v dioxane-water medium.

Results and Discussion

The stability constants were calculated from the titration data by the well established method of Irving and Rossotti². The values of $\bar{n}_A$ at various corrected pH values as determined by the method of Irving and Mahnot⁶ were compiled from the titration data and a curve of $\bar{n}_A$ values against the corresponding pH was plotted. The formation curve extended over a range of $0.1 < \bar{n}_A < 1$ (Fig.1), indicating the dissociation of phenolic hydrogen with the formation of species LH only. The value of pK_1 , which corresponds to phenolic H, was evaluated from the half-integral point at $\bar{n}_A = 0.5$. The linear plot of $\log \bar{n}_A / (1 - \bar{n}_A)$ vs pH was also drawn to corroborate the value found by half-integral method. The two values agree well. From the titration data, $\bar{n}$ and pL values were calculated. The $\bar{n}$ values were plotted against the corresponding

Fig. 1. Formation curve of 4-hydroxy-3-aldehydobiphenyl.

pL values to get the formation curves of the metal complexation equilibria (Fig. 2). The values of stability constants $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were determined from these formation curves. The plots of $\log(\bar{n}/1-\bar{n})$ and $\log(2-\bar{n}/\bar{n}-1)$ vs pH were also drawn for these systems. The values of $\log K_1$ and

representative values are recorded in Table 1. The order of stability constants was found to be $Cu > Zn > Co > Ni > Mg$.

Fig. 2. Metal-ligand systems of 4-hydroxy-3-aldehydophenyl.

$\log K_2$ evaluated from these plots agree well with those obtained by half-integral method. In the case of Mg^{2+} where the difference between $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ was less than 1.78 log units the least square treatment was applied to obtain more accurate values. The limits of error⁷ and the standard deviation⁸ for log K values were determined. The most

TABLE 1—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF VARIOUS COMPLEXES

	$t=30 \pm 0.1^\circ$		$\mu=0.1 M (NaClO_4)$			
	H ⁺	Cu ²⁺	Ni ²⁺	Co ²⁺	Zn ²⁺	Mg ²⁺
$\log K_1$	9.87	7.98	5.12	5.46	6.16	3.64
$\log K_2$	—	6.07	—	—	—	3.54
Standard deviation	± 0.04	± 0.06	± 0.05	± 0.12	± 0.06	± 0.05
Limit of error	± 0.02	± 0.03	± 0.03	± 0.14	± 0.04	± 0.02

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